

TARA_	YYYY	MM	DD	PORT (CITY)	LAT DD	MM.MMM	LONG DDD	MM.MMM
Start	2021	03	21	Puerto Montt	S 41	28.000	W 72	53.000
End	2021	04	07	Concepcion	S 36	42.000	W 73	06.000

CAMPAING OBJECTIVE

The objective of this leg was to make continuous measurements along surface water with the underway system (salinity, temperature, pH, pCO₂) and stations along and across the coastal ocean in the central-southern Chile. In each station (9 total stations) we deployed the rosette+ctd instrument to measure the physicochemical characteristics and to sample water in different depth for genomics, transcriptomics, nutrients, pH, TA, DOC, POC, pigments, etc, from the surface to 500 meters depth. Also we deployed several nets with differents mesh size (from 20 micrometers to 680 micrometers) in the surface and in the vertical column water to collect microorganisms.

PARTICIPANTS

	ROLE	NAME, Surname, Affiliation
1	CREW - Captain	Samuel Audrain
2	CREW - 1st Officer	Nicolas BIN/Yves Tournon (since the 04/04/2021)
3	CREW -	David MONMARCHE
4	CREW -	François AURAT
5	CREW -	Loïc CAUDAN
6	CREW - Cook	Sophie BIN
7	CREW - Media	Maeva BARDY
8	GUEST	Laurianne Clément/Wilfried N'Sondé (since 04/04/2021)
9	SCIENCE - A - Oceano. Engineer	Josep Erta
10	SCIENCE - B - Chief Scientist	Emilio Alarcón
11	SCIENCE - C - W-Lab genomics	Eric Tavernier
12	SCIENCE - D - S-Lab biogeochemistry	Douglas COUET
13	SCIENCE - E - S-Lab sorting/imaging	Milena CERDA
14	Observer from the SHOA	Josseline Fernández

ENVIRONMENTAL CONTEXT

The extensive coast along of Chile allows us to investigate several oceanographical features, particularly the upwelling events influencing the coastal water. The surface waters of northern and central-south of Chile is dominated by the Humboldt Current with a colder and less saline sub-antarctic waters (SAAW). Below this SAAW, we can find the Equatorial Sub-surface Waters (ESSW) with more saline waters, with high concentrations of nutrients, high in CO₂ concentrations, and very low in oxygen concentrations (known as Oxygen Minimum Zone) that feed the upwelling events along the Chilean Coast. Also, in this zone (Concepción), we have a particular topography with a submarine canyon. The knowledge of the influence of the canyon on the OMZ and upwelling events is little. This cruise and the chosen site of the different stations aimed at understanding better these oceanographic processes.

Figure: Major oceanographic features along the Chilean Coast show the Humboldt current and upwelling events in the study zone (modified from Acha et al 2004).

MAJOR ACHIEVEMENTS & SCIENTIFIC INTERESTS

The study area is one of more productive zone in the world, with large fisheries of sardine, anchoveta and hake. This productivity are sustained principally by large biomass of phytoplankton, dominated by diatoms, during the upwelling events with deep waters very rich in nutrients . However, the upwelling is seasonal in this area, depending of the south wind that is more intense during spring and summer seasons. Fortunately, the south wind was dominant during this leg and allowed us to observe and sample during an upwelling event. Also, at station 20, we could observe an OMZ and sample it.

SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES

Provide overview of sampling activities during the Campaign.

Station ###	Date (Z=UTC) YYYYMMDDZ	Latitude	Longitude	CAST – Z00-Z10	CAST – Z00-D1	NET – WPII 20 - Horizontal	NET – WPII 20 - vertical	NET – WPII 200 - Horizontal	NET – WPII 200 - Vertical	CAST – Z00-D2	CAST – Z00+Z01+Z05	Bow Pole	Microtops	HTSRB	NET – Manta 330	CAST – Z01+Z03+Z05	NET – Régent 680	NET – Régent 680	CAST – Z02+Z04+Z06	Rodrigo' s net 300 – 150 - 0m	Rodrigo' s net 300 – 50 - 0m	CAST – Z07	CAST – Z08	CAST – Z09	CAST – Z10
012	20210322	41° 41.9	74° 7.7	x	x	X	x	X	x	x	x	x			x	x	x	X		X	x				
013	20210324	41° 29.2	74° 39.1	x	x	X	x	X	x	x	X	x			x	x	X	X		x	x	x	x	x	
014	20210325	39° 56.2	74° 43.96	X	X	X	X	X	X	x	X	X				X	X	X		X	x	x	x	x	
015	20210326	40° 5.8	74° 25.1	X	X	X	X	X	X	x	X	X			X	X	X	X		X	x	X	x	x	
016	20210328	40°6.1	74° 1.7	x	x	X	x	X	x	x	x	x			x	x	x	x		x	x	x			
017	20210331	36°59.0	73°54.7	x	x	X	x	X	x	x	x	x			x	x				x	x	x	x	x	
018	20210401	36°48.8	73°26.6	X	X	X	X	X	X	x	X	X				X	X	X		X	x	x	x	x	
019	20210402	36°43.5	73°44.0	X	X	X	X	X	X	x	X	X				X	X	X		X	x	x	x	x	
020	20210403	36°39.0	74°6.7	X	X	X	X	X	X	x	X	X			x	X	X	X		X	x	x	x	x	

